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**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING SCIENCES & RESEARCH
TECHNOLOGY**
**EXPLORING WHICH MATERIAL IS MOST SUITABLE FOR A COUPLING
WHEN IT IS BEING USED IN A TRACTION GEARBOX LOAD TEST**

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ABSTRACT

The following research project aims to find the most suitable material for a coupling when it is being used in a traction gearbox load test. This will be achieved by researching the materials and their properties to see how they would cope being exerted to torque and vibration throughout a load test. Further to this, as well as the couplings being able to be used during test successfully, there will be a system in place to allow the couplings to be hydraulically fitted and removed.

1. INTRODUCTION

When a traction gearbox has failed in service, it requires an inspection due to high vibrations or other potential factors - it must then be overhauled. The most crucial part of the overhaul process is to load test the gearboxes, this is a process where two identical units are used in tandem (one unit running anticlockwise and the other clockwise at similar speeds) to create load to simulate authentic conditions that would be present out on the railway. This process is a key element in the manufacturing process as it will indicate if the units have been assembled correctly and to the right standards.

This research will find a material suitable for a coupling featuring a hydraulic release to be able to withstand the duration and environment of the load test. The solution will be a result of two main areas, researching the material and the hydraulic release to see if it is both feasible and cost effective. Following this, prototypes will be manufactured and tested to see if this is a valid solution after looking at data produced from the test system as well as from a practical point of view.

Research objectives

Figure 1 (below) shows the objectives that were set out at the beginning of the project as they were intended to be met. The primary objective was fulfilled as a coupling has been manufactured from a suitable material whilst meeting the other criterion. However, reflecting on the project and the objectives it was hard to measure how efficient the new process is compared to the old solutions as each project has a different solution taking a different amount of time so having a fair comparison was not something that was thought about.

2 - Objectives/goals/scope

This research aims to find the most suitable material for the coupling when it is being used during load testing. The material for the new couplings should meet the following criteria:

- It should be lightweight to reduce the strain of manual handling when the coupling is being fitted and removed from the gearbox input shaft.
- Fitting and removal should be carried out with the use of hydraulics to prevent damaging the input stages of the gearboxes, as well as removing the amount of manual handling required in the process.
- The process of fitting and removing the couplings should be more time efficient than the current method being used.
- The solution needs to be cost effective as this is a process that will need to be repeated on more than one type of gear unit.

Figure 1. Research objectives and goals

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rotex Couplings

Rotex couplings are well known for being small, both in mass and dimensions whilst maintaining the characteristics of being able to transmit a large amount of torque. Rotex couplings are primarily used to connect two pieces of machinery together to transmit torque in one direction, but rarely are the couplings used on shafts, in this case gearboxes running in opposite directions, to create load exposing the couplings to large amounts of stress. The Rotex coupling with a rubber element between the jaws are suitable for the application as they are used to reduce the backlash and the amount of direct torque applied to the individual jaws (McCullough, 2000). The use of the Rotex coupling along with the rubber element will be vital in the testing of the gearboxes as they are able to deal with torque along with the reduced backlash, this will prevent there being any damaged to the gearboxes as the couplings are less prone to failing due to the tight tolerance machining and the rubber element. A Rotex coupling is typically manufactured for a specific purpose meaning for the purpose of this research it will be a matter of gathering the requirements of the gearboxes that are going to be part of the standardised process to specify the material of the coupling, the rubber element and then how the hydraulic port will be able to be added into this to combine the different areas.

2.2 Hydraulically fit couplings

Fitting hubs on a shaft with a keyway has always and will remain a popular way to go about this process as it requires no specialist skills that an engineer would not have. However, using hydraulics to remove hubs from shafts can bring a lot of concern, mainly for safety due to the high pressures involved with this. Not only is it safety factor but using hydraulics to remove hubs (couplings in the case of this research) comes with specialist training and equipment which contributes to the financial viability of using this process (Calistrat, 1993). Keyless couplings are only to be used only on tapered shafts as this creates an interference normally between 0.0635mm and 0.0500mm, any more interference than this can cause an increase in stress which can then lead to failures. The interference leaves enough room for the hydraulic oil to bridge the gap between the coupling and the shaft, then using a hydraulic ram the coupling can be moved to the end of the taper (Calistrat, 1993).

Hydraulically fit couplings are less prone to failure providing that the material, machining, and the fitment is correct, this is all true until they are overloaded with torque thus leading them to fail. This makes keyed couplings less superior as they have a large weak spot which is, they key and keyway. The keyway and key combination can cause excessive misalignment and movement as the interference is often not as tight, this becomes an issue in service when the machinery is vibrating causing the coupling to move on the shaft slowly damaging the key which eventually will break leading to a failure (Locke, 2013).

2.3 Material

It is noted in the research that using the incorrect material combined with a hydraulic release can cause the coupling to split in half as it is fitted (Calistrat, 1993), this makes the material selection essential. Further to this there are weak points on the coupling also known as the jaws which are alleviated of stress by the rubber element.

The typical coupling is manufactured from the following materials cast iron, nodular iron, sintered steel, and aluminium (KTR, 2021), the materials that the couplings are manufactured from are a limiting factor on the research as far as physical testing is concerned, but theoretical testing can use the results as a baseline which will then be worked from if required.

Regardless of the application of the coupling the material needs to be suitable for the application as this will either withstand the load being applied during the application or it will fail immediately or fail over time both causing costly damage. It has been noted in other research that overtime and excessive use of couplings in high vibration environments can cause them to start to crack and fail in ways which cannot always be seen by the human eye. As the damage has not been seen the couplings are reused eventually leading to failure. This will have to be a consideration in the research as damage might not be seen in the first tests of the couplings, but it could still be present (Tripp, Kim, & Whitney, 1993).

3. METHODOLOGY

When working on each stage of the research project there was a combination of theoretical and practical testing and development, this also allowed the project to be influenced by primary and secondary research. This was at each stage for the coupling type, the material, and the implementation of the hydraulic release port. By looking at each individual section as its own sub-project it will allow for a more robust solution.

The first step for the project is to look at the existing solutions that are being used already in gearbox load testing. This will demonstrate the positives and the negatives of the current equipment highlighting what necessary improvements will need to be made in terms of coupling type and material properties. Further to this the data gathered for the current equipment can be gathered and compared to the prototype to see if there are any improvements or areas of regression.

Following the review of the existing equipment the process of looking for a new coupling type, the material which the coupling needs to be manufactured from and the implementation of the hydraulic port can then be looked at. The material testing will comprise of computerised testing which will provide useful information opposed to increasing the project's budget on purchasing physical material that will be tested, the material will also be researched through research articles and books. This will then lead to the manufacturing and testing of the final coupling.

3.1 Existing solutions

3.1.1 Material

Researching the material that is being used in the existing test equipment was a vital part of the research as it is an area that has not previously been investigated. After sending off a piece of tooling for material inspection it was found that all test equipment has always been manufactured from BS EN 10025 S355 J2+N, this is a low carbon steel with a medium tensile strength (Steel express, 2021). This means it is like mild steel but as this is J2, the material is useful in below freezing conditions, which is a great property to have but not relevant in this case. Upon physical research, the tooling manufactured from this material was heavy and when manual handling it would require two hands and the correct manual handling techniques. This is one of the project objectives, reducing the amount of manual handling strain.

3.1.2 Connection

It was important to research why and how the current test equipment is being used to couple gearboxes together to understand why this has been done and why there has not been an alternative method implemented.

On one gearbox project the two gearboxes are connected by using a hollow shaft that is connected to the final coupling they are sent out with via nuts and bolts as seen in figure 2. This posed some very important questions for the project around health and safety failures and quality assurance. The nuts and bolts are torqued up to 75 Nm, however when the shafts are spinning in excess of 1000 rpm the fasteners are exposed to a lot of vibrations which could work the connections loose as there is no sealant such as Loctite to keep the connection safe. This can then lead to the shaft becoming loose and causing damage to the product, which has cost implications, and damage to the test equipment that can cause all production to come to a halt. The removal of mechanical fasteners is another objective of the project as after this investigation there are more risks involved than positives.

Figure 2

3.1.3 Positives & negatives

A review of the current testing equipment proved extremely useful as it confirmed that the tooling needs to be improved in line with the objectives that were originally set out in the project plan.

The main positives that came from reviewing the equipment were that by using the couplings that the gearboxes were supplied with ensured that the shafts that the couplings are sat on were never damaged. However, as the final couplings were used before the gearboxes were sent out it means that they had already been used and this could cause conflicting opinions on whether the organisation were brand new when they arrived with the customer.

When reviewing the test equipment, it pointed out that there are a few drawbacks. In some tests toothed couplings are used with mechanical fasteners and once the test had ended there was slight damage found on the teeth. This is not an issue as the damage is minor however, this means that eventually the teeth will wear away and possibly cause a failure that will have consequences.

3.2 Research / development

3.2.1 Material

For the new material to meet the brief it had to be lightweight for easy manual handling as this would be the easiest and most effective way to put the coupling onto the shaft. After conducting some computer simulation as seen in figures 3 & 4 below shows that there is one major weak point in the couplings which is on the teeth. However, this will be overcome through the use of a rubber element which will reduce the amount of torque that each tooth is exerted too.

Figure 3. Diecast aluminium coupling, computer simulation

Figure 4. Low carbon steel, computer simulation

Experimenting with low carbon steel and then die-cast aluminium yielded similar results, the only noticeable difference being that the die-cast aluminium coupling had more stress on slightly more surface of the coupling tooth. The simulation was carried out on the two materials as these are the two coupling materials that match the budget whilst keeping machining costs down

3.2.2 Coupling type

The primary research that took place on investigating the current solution proved useful when it came to developing a new solution for several reasons. It first showed that there needed to be a connection between the two gearboxes that was not through mechanical fasteners as they can often be unreliable when exposed to large amounts of vibrations. Additionally, it also showed how this can contribute toward quality issues by using new couplings during the test phase that are then sent on to the final customer.

Secondary research contributed to the type of coupling that was going to be used in the application as Rotex couplings are used for connecting shafts together but not necessarily underload as they will be used in this application. Using computer simulation to see whether the Rotex coupling will be able to withstand the torque before going into prototyping was an essential part of the process.

3.2.3 Hydraulic release

With the research conducted into how a hydraulic release would work in a coupling and a shaft, it took further working out on where the port would need to be situated. The shafts that are going to be used in conjunction with the coupling are all tapered 1:100 this is seen in figure 5 below. This means that when the coupling is gently placed on the shaft it will stop on the taper and by this point the hydraulic port should be passed the shaft end to allow the pressure to build and be pressed on. If the hydraulic port is not passed the shaft end, then it means there will be a leak of hydraulic oil and the coupling would be deemed useless.

Figure 5

3.3 Manufacturing and testing

With the material type and the position of the hydraulic port decided upon after computer simulation exercises it was time to get the prototype manufactured. The machinist company was then contacted once I had acquired a quote for the works with an engineering drawing of the coupling with the hydraulic fitting as seen below in figure 6.

Figure 6. Engineering drawing of die-cast aluminium coupling with hydraulic release

Once the coupling had come back from machining it was time to test the first prototype to see if the research had formed a practical solution that would work. As this was the first time the coupling was going to be put onto a gear unit's shaft it was decided upon that a scrap shaft would be used to ensure that if the coupling was not suitable it would not create cost penalties. Using a hydraulic ram and oil expansion the coupling was then fitted onto the shaft as seen in Figure 7.

Figure 7. Prototype coupling being fit on to the scrap shaft for the first time

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Results

Once the prototype had been tested it was found that the research and the result of the research might not have been as accurate as originally intended. This is because when the coupling needed to be removed from the scrap shaft it was not coming off as it would have been expected with the hydraulic release. The coupling had to have heat applied to it and be removed with pullers as it became stuck. There were two possible reasons for this happening, firstly, the research had not picked up on factors such as thermal expansion of the shaft and the coupling was too tight, or that the coupling was not machined correctly, and it was a manufacturing error.

Once the coupling had been removed it became apparent that it was indeed a manufacturing error and that it needed to be rectified before using it on a live gearbox awaiting test. The extent of the damage to the coupling can be seen below in figure 8 which shows that the taper on the coupling was too steep meaning when it had been pressed on it had slightly deformed. Despite there being a manufacturing error, this damage confirms that the aluminium up to this point was the correct material, this is because if there are any errors the coupling will fail before the shaft is damaged as the aluminium is softer than the hardened steel that the shafts are manufactured from.

Figure 8. Confirmation that there had been a manufacturing error

When it was decided that it was a manufacturing error the couplings were sent back to the machinists where the error was rectified and was machined again correctly. Manufacturing errors were identified as a risk to the project both in cost and time, however as the machinists were contacted the same day this problem was rectified within three days, which did not prove to be critical.

When the coupling was returned from the machinists it was tested in the same manner giving the team the results that was originally intended. The couplings were then fit to the live gear units as seen in figure 9 with the rubber element to reduce torque transmission.

Figure 9. Couplings successfully on the live units ready for test

4.2 Speed and torque

Once the couplings had been set up, the test could commence and gather the data to suggest whether the couplings are suitable for the task or if they are not fit for purpose. Below in figure 10 is the speed and torque data.

Figure 10. Speed and torque test data

From the data collected in the test it was noted that the couplings were able to withstand the speed and torque that they were being exerted to. The speed and torque that is being output in this test is the most that the couplings will ever be subject too. Other gear units are not as big and therefore do not have over 1169Nm of torque running through them at 490rpm. This was confirmation that the die-cast aluminium couplings would be suitable for the required speed and torque.

4.3 Vibration

It was hard to specifically measure the vibration of the couplings as this would pose a massive health and safety risk and it also is not possible with the testing facility that was used for this research. The test system is an enclosed space where no one can be inside whilst the motor and gear units are running, this is because if something is to go wrong it could prove to be fatal. The vibration data is collected by heavy duty magnetic sensors which are attached to the gearbox housing for the most accurate results, the sensors historically used were not as heavy duty and would often provide false readings as they would move around because of the vibrations.

However, the data collected for vibrations was on the gearboxes and the couplings combined. If the couplings were misaligned and not seated correctly the gearboxes would not run correctly causing the gearbox to fail the test. As we can see in figure 11 below the vibrations from the test are uniform at each stage of the test, showing that there was no issue of power transmission between the couplings. Once the units got up to speed, they stayed at roughly 8.5 m/s which is a pass as the fail rate is at 12m/s, the data shows at three points that the units failed due to vibration issues. This was discounted because when the units stop and change direction it is a mechanical movement of the gears getting rid of the backlash before spinning in the opposite direction. This would have been concerning if the team had never load tested gearboxes before but because they have this happens in every test so the anomalies here were discounted too.

Figure 11. Vibration testing for the rotex couplings

4.4 Research outcome

Despite the project being held up by a pandemic in some places such as manufacturing due to staff being off, the project has been able to be completed within the given time with the desired result of having implemented a solution that works.

Through the data that was collected it was obvious to see that the couplings have served their purpose and proved to be effective. This was confirmed by the data in both the vibration, speed & torque graphs. The die-cast aluminium coupling met the objectives outlined in the project plan as it is lightweight and has a functioning hydraulic release.

There was one limitation when collecting the data to see whether or not the temperature would lead to enough thermal expansion for the coupling to not contact the taper on the shaft. This would lead to the coupling slipping and causing damage meaning there would be no immediate way to test the gear units that the customers require. Another benefit of this research is that all of the information that has been gathered for the material and coupling type can be applied to other projects that might vary from the standard design, this means that replicating the research on a different scale would not mean starting from the beginning.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

The outcome of this project was more than favourable due to the successful outcome and data collection to back it up. Though there could have been areas in the project that could have been more controlled which is in hindsight easier to correct. Reflecting on the project there have been many different areas that have required different types of communication skills with both internal and external stakeholders. Time management skills have been fundamental throughout the project to ensure that the critical path has been maintained and not caused any issues despite errors at the machining phase.

A detrimental part of the project was at the machining phase where the couplings were found to have been machined incorrectly, this was a risk identified but was not deemed to be very likely. This brought some very valuable lessons as there could have been more mitigation involved to avoid this issue in the first place. In hindsight for this myself and a colleague would have been to go and see the machinists in person to have a walk around, chat and an overall feel for the quality of the work and workshop. This would have been a valid solution but due to the Coronavirus pandemic this was not possible, so all communication was conducted over the phone and emails. Further to this had we had a CNC machine on site I would have been able to conduct the machining myself which would be a quality control factor so there would be no reliance on a third party.

This was a valuable lesson to learn when dealing with projects and third parties as it showed that contingency both in time and cost are crucial. Without building the contingency into the project it means that there cannot be any errors and if there are the project will not be able to go ahead as planned.

There was not a main contributing factor towards enhancing personal performance throughout this project but there were small individual factors that really helped push the project towards success. Managing the time for the project was something that I was familiar with as this is part of my role at work. I manage work packages for projects to ensure that they are going to be complete before the project is live, preventing any delays, so when it came to managing time in this project the Gantt chart was useful and my communication skills with the team were well received. Another factor was that I have been around testing of gearboxes prior to the project starting which meant that I had a foundation on which to build from which showed direction. This helped me appreciate that if the project is being led by someone who has existing knowledge in the area everything will run much smoother opposed to conducting a literature review to get an appreciation of the research, opposed to reviewing literature with some background knowledge.

It was noticed that when a gearbox and motor assembly were running in service that the couplings were failing due to a high increase in torque coming from the traction converter unit in the train, causing major financial and time losses to the operating companies. It was noted that the material was failing causing the couplings to fracture thus not operating and transmitting the power as they should. To prevent this failing the coupling had to be modified, the modification was a slipping bush that would be an interface between the coupling hub and the

gearbox output shaft. This means that when /if the high torque was to be exerted again the coupling hub would slip on the slipping bush to prevent any sudden movement of the coupling to cause the material to fail. There hasn't been further investigation into the couplings failing ever since this engineering change.

The relevance of this to the research project is that the material that the coupling was manufactured is softer than the hardened shaft meaning that the coupling would spin on the shaft as opposed to failing and causing damage to the gearbox input shaft.

Although not a showstopper but a hindrance was the Coronavirus pandemic throughout this project. The pandemic meant that colleges were closed meaning that access to facilities such as the library which would have been useful during the literature review were closed. Also as mentioned previously, quality checking the machinists would have been a useful step to prevent quality issues as well as having a face-to-face meeting with them so they can have an appreciation for the work opposed to all communication being through virtual communication.

DECLARATION

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